

Deliverable [1.3]

Definition of strategies that support and underpin complete academic environments

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Summary

A guiding principle of the common research and innovation agenda to be delivered in TRAIN is the concept of a 'complete academic environment' (CAE), which focuses on the importance of the interconnections between research, education, and innovation to the mutual benefit and increased impact of the universities' core missions. Complete academic environments contribute to cross-boundary research and collaborative education and are also characterised by cooperation with public and private actors from across society. This integrated approach capitalises on synergies and supports the development, evaluation and dissemination of new modalities and methodologies of collaboration.¹

This report aims to clarify the concept of a complete academic environment and its aim to increase the relevance and impact of education and research by deepening collaboration with society (industry, non-profit, non-governmental and governments) and to suggest a strategic framework for them.

The proposed strategic framework presented in this report includes three pillars: *Competence development*, *Pathways to impact* and *Incentives*. Each pillar includes possible activities and effects on different levels. Together the pillars create a suggested institutional framework for the achievement and success of complete academic environments. Developing complete academic environments based on this framework will allow the EUTOPIAN alliance and its institutes to implement a structural way of coordinating and engaging the academic resources and capabilities within our universities, in order to deliver and increase the impact from research, education and innovation in a challenge-led and innovative manner.

During the rest of the TRAIN project the EUTOPIA alliance will further discuss and anchor the framework and adjust if needed, with the intention of including it in the common research and innovation agenda.

¹ EUTOPIA TRAIN (Project Number 101017419) Grant Agreement p. 9

Introduction

The overall aim of work package 1 in TRAIN is to develop an overarching Research and Innovation Agenda for the EUTOPIA alliance and to share learnings from this development with key stakeholders. This will underpin a common approach to strengthening research capacity, impact, and efficiency across the alliance. This integrated approach capitalises on synergies and supports the development, evaluation and dissemination of new modalities and methodologies of collaboration.

A guiding principle of TRAIN's common research and innovation agenda is the concept of a 'complete academic environment', which focuses on the importance of the interconnections between research, education, and innovation to the mutual benefit of all activities. Complete academic environments contribute to cross-boundary research and collaborative education; they are also characterised by cooperation with public and private actors from across society engaged with research, education and innovation activities.

With 'innovation' we mean, in a broad sense, the implementation of academic knowledge and knowledge-based assets and solutions outside of academia; not only technical products, but also other results of research, including social sciences, humanities and arts – and not only through commercialization, but also through other pathways to impact, e.g. various forms of collaboration with societal organisations.

The importance of equipping the European research and education communities with the tools and expertise required to address economic and societal challenges is widely acknowledged (EU New innovation agenda², ERA³ etc). The Horizon Europe programme also emphasises the importance of challenge-led research and the adoption of coordinated approaches to the deployment of academic resources and capabilities to deliver positive change.

Given the ever-rising expectations on universities to contribute to the resolution of challenging societal issues, and to the development and deployment of new talent and new knowledge, there is a need to establish principles, strategies and procedures for collaboration. Setting overarching principles for the plethora of collaboration activities in academic institutions will contribute to that collaboration and be mutually beneficial to universities and partners in society alike. It is important that high standards of integrity and relevance are maintained, and that the university understands that collaboration does not undermine its role as a provider of reliable and public knowledge.

² New European Innovation Agenda [New European Innovation Agenda \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/en/press-communications/inline/2020/06/1019223.pdf)

³ European Research Area https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-area_en

What is a complete academic environment?

The overall aim of complete academic environments is to increase the relevance and impact of education, research and innovation by deepening collaboration – both between these activities within the academic institutions and with societal partners (industry, non-profit, non-governmental and governments). The complete academic environment concept is central to the design and delivery of EUTOPIA TRAIN, and the EUTOPIA alliance sees the development of complete academic environments as a prerequisite for mutual development and the strengthening of education, research and innovation for the benefit of the society as a whole.

A complete academic environment interconnects research, education, innovation and cooperation with society at large and is seen by students and staff as their natural studying and working environment. Such academic environments actively cultivate and contribute to cross-disciplinary research and collaborative education, and actively support innovation and cooperation with public and private actors from across society. All education – regardless of level – is linked to research, and all research is linked to education. This is a key feature of the EUTOPIA alliance since its start, which will be further developed over the coming years. A complete academic environment makes use of co-creation and collaboration skills within the areas of research, education and innovation, to connect – within a field, a subject, within an academic institution, between academic institutions and/or alliances, or to societal actors – and to attain relevant impact.

The suggested framework presented in this report will enable the development and strengthening of complete academic environments within our institutions – in order to structure and enhance the quality and quantity of our overall sustainable and responsible impact. The report is also a starting point for the integration of complete academic environments within the common research and innovation agenda of the EUTOPIA alliance.

Connections to the helix innovation model

The complete academic environment within a higher education institution is a precondition for a robust and reciprocal linkage between public bodies/government, academia/universities, and industry; previously referred to as the triple helix model. This model acknowledged the importance of higher education for innovation, in the perspective of the ‘knowledge economy’.

The helix model has evolved since it was formulated in the 1990s and although it has been widely adopted, a fourth helix was added in 2009. The addition was an attempt to broaden the context beyond the economy in the perspective of a ‘knowledge society’. The addition included the media-

based and culture-based public (also ‘civil society’), arguing that the ‘innovation culture’ is one of the keys for a ‘democracy of knowledge’.⁴

The model has further evolved into a quintuple helix innovation model, which stresses the necessary socioecological transition of society and economy by adding the dimension of the environment. The quintuple helix supports the formation of a win-win situation between ecology, knowledge, and innovation, creating synergies between economy, society, and democracy. The quintuple helix model therefore underpins the EUTOPIAN values.⁵

If the helix model represents the interactions between the different stakeholders within a society – the complete academic environment is an attempt to describe the ideal skills set and facilitation mechanisms within the universities to consciously, proactively and responsibly act on those interactions. The complete academic environment is therefore a precondition for our alliance’s participation in the helix model and for the realisation of our commitment to tackle planetary and democratic challenges.

The framework proposed in this report is based on an understanding of the dilemmas and challenges for academic institutions and academics to take active part in the quintuple helix model, including not only knowledge transfer and exchange, but also collaboration and co-creation of knowledge.

⁴ Carayannis, E.G. and Campbell, D.F.J. (2009) ‘Mode 3’ and ‘Quadruple Helix’: toward a 21st century fractal innovation ecosystem’, *Int. J. Technology Management*, Vol. 46, Nos. 3/4, pp.201–234

⁵ EUTOPIA Values Statement: <https://eutopia-university.eu/english-version/about-us/about-us/values-statement>.

The dilemma(s)

There are great, and increasing, demands on academia to contribute to the implementation of the *Sustainable Development Goals* and the overall impact in society. Increasingly, HEIs are being seen as a source of talent, entrepreneurship, future-oriented innovation, and a lead player in collaborations for regional development. The helix model of innovation was and is an attempt to describe and analyse how this can be achieved by all involved parties.

However, realising this potential persists due to several dilemmas. HEIs and academics struggle to balance the oft-contradictory expectations placed upon them navigating political demands vs academic values and institutional form; excellence-driven incentive systems and funding schemes; top-down and bottom-up research, basic, translational, and applied research, etc. If education and research within HEIs are supposed to have a wider and larger economic, societal and political impact – one that is not only about increasing the number of patents and commercial innovations – whilst staying true to its core mission, to educate and research – there is a need for a cultural development within the institutions.

Many obstacles are related to collaboration between academia and societal actors (including e.g. industry, non-profit, non-governmental and governments). There is a big gap between the collaboration strategies of both HEIs and external organisations and the actual activities taking place; the majority of academics and business do not engage in collaborations with each other, and those that do still acknowledge that doing so is not easy.

Studies have shown that this limited engagement leads to insufficient relevance of academic study programmes, low employability of graduates, and a vastly unused potential of societal impact of research. A lack of interaction between civil society and universities/industry can result in the failure of innovations to address societal challenges properly, and a lack of necessary support to enable their broad uptake. A paucity of interactions with public bodies can also weaken evidence-based policy making and lead to less informed and potentially misaligned regulations.⁶

Both academics/HEI managers and business have previously stated lack of funding and resources as one of the main barriers to cooperation. Academics also raise bureaucracy and lack of time to work collaboratively as the main barriers, while external actors highlight cultural differences and differing motivations. Although the merit system has been well-debated, the academic career structure has not yet (uniformly) incorporated skills or training in impact. Combined with bureaucratic obstacles this also creates considerable inertia in the development of impact and innovation.

⁶ Karen: O'Dwyer, M., Filieri, R. & O'Malley, L. Establishing successful university–industry collaborations: barriers and enablers deconstructed. *J Technol Transf* (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-022-09932-2>; The State of University-Business Cooperation in Europe. http://publications.europa.eu/resource/cellar/1b03ee59-67a4-11e8-ab9c-01aa75ed71a1.0001.01/DOC_1

It is evident that given the right circumstances, which includes both drivers and facilitation to fuel UBCs, collaboration can be a highly positive activity for all parties involved, and for society as a whole. In addition, once such collaborations are established, they give rise to new forms of collaborations, as an academic or business that collaborate in one way are more likely to collaborate in others.

Thus, policy development to increase overall impact should not just focus on removing the barriers, but also on developing the incentives towards cooperation and on establishing transdisciplinary environments around research, education and innovation, nurturing sustainable and mutually beneficial relationships rather than individual transactions. This aligns well with the development and strengthening of complete academic environments.

Proposed framework to underpin and support complete academic environments

To create the best conditions and a sustainable culture for complete academic environments, in light of the dilemmas and challenges identified both by us and others, we propose the following pillars around which to structure the strategic framework: *Competence development*, *Pathways to impact* and *Incentives*.

The three pillars align well with the recommendations for public research organisations, including universities, outlined in the recently proposed *Guiding principles for knowledge valorisation*, which was adopted in August by the European Commission³.

The principles recommend that universities foster the development of entrepreneurial skills, practices, and processes – as well as those that facilitate engagement with citizens, civil society and policy makers – set up mobility schemes, and crosslink different areas and sectors.

The principles also strongly emphasise that universities and other public research organisations, transition from straightforward protection and transferral of Intellectual Property Rights to a broader, more comprehensive management of all knowledge-based intellectual assets and tacit knowledge. This includes developing and working with a greater diversity of pathways for socioeconomic value creation, to accommodate those disciplines and solutions that have not been as well-represented in academic innovation, to fully leverage the impact potential of academic knowledge on society.

The principles also highlight the importance of identifying and acknowledging the reciprocal value that is created for the good of research and education when engaging in innovation and collaboration activities, and of developing additional incentive systems (including within research funding) to ensure that students and staff learn and practice knowledge valorisation.

In essence, both innovation and entrepreneurial skills should lie very close to the researchers' and teachers' ordinary skill set (novelty and problem-solving focus, experiment-based hypothesis testing, iteration and learning, and independently attracting resources to develop these skills further), but the differences in culture, motivation and language are barriers preventing many researchers from seeing themselves as entrepreneurial. And it is evident that many academics still do not possess the skills, ability and motivation to network and interact effectively with the societal users of research-based innovations in a co-creational manner.⁷ Thus, there is a call for a development of a new skill set in the complete academic environment.

⁷ MacGregor et al., [2010](#); Miller et al., [2014](#)

In a complete academic environment, collaborative, entrepreneurial and innovative skills as well as citizens science, are developed and integrated into its core operations, on its own terms. This is to make sure that the incentives and strategic choices for enabling innovation, outreach, co-creation with external organisations and citizens, and impact align with the goals for research and education in a sustainable way.

“Impact” should be understood in its broadest sense, i.e. scientific, social, economic, political, environmental etc. It should be seen as a pathway toward a desired (long term) objective. Therefore, it is in the interest of the EUTOPIA-alliance to continue to support all types of research, i.e. research focusing on relevance or application in society, and research that focuses on excellence and achieving scientific breakthroughs. Research in different phases, with different motivations and goals, e.g. ‘basic research’ or ‘applied research’ should not be opposed, as various forms of research are needed to contribute to a complete academic environment.

A broader view of pathways to impact in the complete academic environment model also calls for the development of support systems regarding intellectual property rights, from a technology & knowledge transfer, transactions-based logic to an adaptive support system that both can develop the competence and capacity for innovation and impact of the HEI, and facilitate and manage a plethora of impact-aiming collaboration and innovation initiatives rising from the complete academic environment, including open science.

PROPOSED OVERARCHING PRINCIPLES FOR THE FRAMEWORK

The anticipated activities for the framework follow principles already defined in different EUTOPIA projects (2050, TRAIN, MORE), including:

- A balance between bottom-up and top-down developed initiatives under the competence development, pathways to collaboration, incentives pillars;
- Involvement of internal and external stakeholders in developing initiatives to support complete academic environments
- Development of initiatives based on needs identified at different levels and stakeholder types
- Transparency and sharing of good practices and activities existent in EUTOPIA member universities
- Growing together as an alliance while also giving the space for specific activities developed at local and national level
- Mutualizing locally existing expertise and leveraging the existing strengths in each institution

As previously mentioned, to create the best conditions and a sustainable culture for complete academic environments we propose the following pillars around which to structure the strategic framework: *Competence development*, *Pathways to impact* and *Incentives*.

Each pillar comes with a different set of proposed activities and answer to key questions such as:

- What kind of competence development is needed to implement CAEs?
- How do we implement CAEs (pathways to impact)?

- How can we encourage and support the implementation process in each institution and at the alliance level (incentives)?

PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

Competence development	Pathways to impact	Incentives
Refers to the need for and importance of nurturing competences that would support the development and implementation of complete academic environments.	Refers to the need for a structured way to develop and manage processes for successful collaboration, valorisation and impact. Collaboration as seen in the complete academic environments cover collaboration both within and outside academia. Impact should be understood in its broadest sense, i.e. scientific, social, economic, political, environmental etc.	Refers to the need for incentives as motivators to stimulate greater output and advancement in developing and implementing complete academic environments (for researchers: cultures, values, access to funds)

We anticipate a series of activities that will be needed in order to implement each of the three pillars. The proposed activities are not to be confused with specific initiatives/sub-activities/examples of good practices already under implementation within TRAIN or to be developed in the future, e.g. Young Leaders Academy training, Connected research communities incubators etc.

PROPOSED ACTIVITIES, TOOLS AND INDICATORS

Competence development	Measurement tools	Indicators
Institutional/alliance level		
Gather input on competences needed to advance complete academic environments (students, researchers, staff)	Questionnaires, focus groups (internal and external), analysis of reports and studies	No. of respondents Representation of different target groups and alliance members No. of analysed reports and studies Report on mapping of needs
Analyse the current practices and topics for competence development	Questionnaires, Analysis of training strategies	Mapping of current practices and topics for competence development
Analyse what types of competence development courses could be set up online, hybrid and/or in-person	Questionnaires, focus groups	Proposal on online, hybrid and/or in-person competence development courses to be set up

Testing and improving the training sessions	Online platform, facilitation, questionnaires	No. of courses tested No. of courses improved Documented versions of courses Inventory of courses
Individual level		
Self-evaluation of competences	Questionnaires	Tool for self-evaluation No. of times of downloaded tool for self-evaluation
Development of competences (for the three target groups; students, researchers, other staff)	Online platform, in person-training sessions	No. of persons starting and finishing courses No. of started and finished courses

Pathways to Impact	Measurement tools	Indicators
Gather best practices on methods used inside the alliance for the advancement of complete academic environments	Questionnaires, interviews	Mapping of best practices No of best practices
Analyse and compile internal best practices	Reports	Mapping of best practices
Analyse and benchmark best practices from other alliances	Reports, interviews	Mapping of best practices
Analysing already documented reports presenting barriers in setting up collaborations and looking at potential solutions to be used in smoothing the work processes	Reports, focus groups	Mapping of best practices
Create a catalogue of best practices of pathways for supporting and developing CAE		Catalogue of best practices

Incentives	Measurement tools	Indicators
Collect and analyse reports presenting barriers in setting up collaborations and looking at potential incentives to be used in smoothing the work processes	Reports	Reports of the analyse highlighting potential incentives
Gather good practices on incentives at institutional level	Questionnaire, interviews	List of good practices
Gather input from internal and external stakeholders, while considering the different institutional levels and structures, on what constitutes an incentive in strengthening and developing CAE	Questionnaire, interviews	List of gathered good practices

Create a list of best practices of incentives for supporting and developing CAE	Lists, reports, questionnaires, interviews	Final list of best practices
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TOOLS

The tools are meant to aid in the accomplishment of initiatives included in the three pillars. They can have different forms, from self-evaluations on competence development needs to training sessions and learning by doing activities.

Strengthening and developing CAEs is a continuous and fast-evolving process requiring the development of tools on an ongoing basis. The tools will need to adapt in order to be useful and relevant to issues as they arise and it is therefore impossible to present an exhaustive list. Nevertheless, the following points set out a series of tools that could be used in the work with the different pillars within CAE.

Tools supporting Competence development:

- Online course sessions for development of competences supporting the implementation of complete academic environments
- GLENN offices for researchers

Tools supporting Pathways to impact:

- Common entry point for external partners (TTO)
- GLENN offices for researchers
- Online R&I Atlas
- Partnering tool
- Catalogue of best practice pathways for supporting and developing CAE

Tools supporting Incentives:

- List of best practice incentives for supporting and developing CAE
- Catalogue of best practice pathways for supporting and developing CAE

EXPECTED RESULTS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF THE FRAMEWORK

Institutional level

- The university is a recurring key partner in collaboration with different stakeholders with focus on local/central government, non-profit/citizen and industry
- More resources (funding, people, infrastructure, etc.) for performing research and education
- Improve and complement our different practices
- Increased relevance, immediacy and immersion of education and research
- Strengthened bonds between academic staff, researchers and students towards a culture of shared practice and innovation

Alliance level

- Strengthen the position of the EUTOPIA alliance as a hub of excellence in innovation, research and education
- Alliance as a tool to showcase the impact of CAE and its results
- Strengthened collaboration with external actors (in terms of new collaborations as well as the quality and sustainability of collaborations)
- Increased influence on European development
- Development of a learning resource opened to all actors active in CAE

Society level

- Increased uptake of education and research (including graduates) by non-academic actors and increased influence on societal development (e.g. policy-making)
- Contributor to solution to global challenges
- Strengthen the links between university and society
- The alliance will take a bigger place in the field of innovation
- Inclusion in the research and innovation process a user-oriented approach whenever possible
- Integrating the environment and SDGs as key aspects in research and innovation

Conclusion

The mission of EUTOPIA alliance, last updated 2022, is to connect communities in order to transform our universities into open, inclusive, diverse and innovative enablers for outreach impact on societies.

The concept of complete academic environments is used here as a method to integrate research, education and innovation (in a broad sense) to create synergies and increase impact both within and outside academia.

While collaboration is often rewarding, it is a complex activity that entails trade-offs of various kinds, ethical dilemmas, and the need for both flexibility and predictability in the interaction with stakeholders and collaboration partners. If collaboration is intended to reinforce quality and afford collaborative networks and real-life problems, carefully crafted procedures are needed to govern and shape collaborative practices.

The proposed framework for increasing impact of research, education and innovation is threefold and include: *Competence development*, *Pathways to impact* and *Incentives*. Each pillar has a set of anticipated activities as well as tools to increase the overall impact on societies. Some of the activities have already been suggested within EUTOPIA2050 and TRAIN. During the rest of the TRAIN project the EUTOPIA alliance will further discuss and anchor the framework and adjust if needed, with the intention of including it in the common research and innovation agenda.